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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
IAM	Identity and Access Management
I-ADOPT	Interoperable Description of Observable Property Terminology framework
BDI	Blue Data Infrastructure
CCP	Cloud Computing Platform
CDI	Common Data Index
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
DO	Digital Object
EDMO	European Directory of Marine Institutions
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
EV	Essential Variable
EXV	Essential Variable vocabulary
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FAIR-IF	FAIR Interoperability Framework
FOSS	Free and Open Source Software

GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GKE	Google Kubernetes Engine
HEU	Horizon Europe
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
maDMP	machine-actionable Data Management Plan
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NODC	National Oceanographic Data Center
NFS	Network File System
NVS	NERC Vocabulary Server
ODV	Ocean Data View
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OIDC	OpenID Connect
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PID	Persistent Identifier
PVC	Persistent Volume Claim
RDA	Research Data Alliance
REST	Representational State Transfer
S3	Amazon Simple Storage Service
SA	Semantic Analyser
SDK	Software Development Kit
SKG	Science Knowledge Graph
SKG-IF	Science Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SQL	Structured Query Language
TA	Transnational Access
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

WOD	World Ocean Database
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Keywords

EOSC; VLabs; Federation; Blue-Cloud VRE;

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The **Blue-Cloud** initiative, launched in 2019 under the EU's Horizon 2020 programme, set out to create a federated ecosystem for marine data and services within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The follow-up project, **Blue-Cloud2026**, is advancing this vision by transforming the initial pilot into a **sustainable, scalable and operational European ecosystem** that delivers FAIR data and analytical services for research on oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters.

At the core of this ecosystem is the **Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)**, which provides an integrated user experience by federating distributed computing resources, analytical platforms and data services. Built on the **D4Science** [1, 2] infrastructure and **gCube** [3] technology, the VRE is accessible through the EOSC Blue-Cloud2026 Gateway and enables Virtual Laboratories (VLabs) that combine data access, processing and collaboration capabilities.

This deliverable describes the **second release of the federated infrastructure**, expanding the federation from initial integration of the Google Cloud Platform and EGI Cloud Compute resources to new federated resources and services, including the operational integration of SOCIB services for Science Knowledge Graphs (SKG), machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) and FAIR assessment capabilities, and the deployment of Beacon technology as high-performance federated subsetting infrastructure enabling fast, parameter-level access to large volumes of heterogeneous marine data and supporting scalable data-lake configurations for WorkBench analytics.

These developments significantly enhance the VRE's ability to support data-intensive scientific workflows and demonstrate the **maturity of the Blue-Cloud federation model**. The federation architecture supports multiple implementation pathways to accommodate heterogeneous e-infrastructures while ensuring a consistent user experience. Overall, this second release demonstrates the **operational consolidation and scalability** of the Blue-Cloud VRE, extending federation from computing resources to **data access, semantic interoperability and service-level integration**. The results strengthen alignment with EOSC and ENVRI initiatives and provide a robust foundation for future expansion, long-term sustainability and broader adoption by the marine research community.

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1. Blueprint for Infrastructure Federation in Blue-Cloud

1.1. Federation Model and Architecture

The Blue-Cloud VRE offers users with an integrated experience across all the applications available, as such, the federation of new resources must retain the seamless access independently of the location of the services or resources. Each participating site providing resources need to provide resources compatible with the deployment of the VRE Analytics Computing Framework services: either as OpenStack projects where the VRE operators can manage Virtual Machines or as Kubernetes clusters that support the execution of container-based applications. A minimum capacity of 256 CPU cores with 512 GB RAM and 10 TB persistent storage is recommended to join the Blue-Cloud VRE. While 256 cores is the target for full-scale VRE support, specific service-hosting (e.g., webODV) can be established on smaller partitions of federated resources.

An additional federation option is considered for third-party services not part of the current Analytics Computing Framework. These can also be incorporated into the VRE offer as long as they are integrated with the Identity and Access Management (IAM) component to ensure a common identity and authorization across them. Integration with IAM uses the well-established OpenID Connect standard¹ which has support across multiple applications and application frameworks. For those applications that do not support OpenID Connect, a Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) proxy based on NGINX is available, so the authorization is managed externally to the application and still accessible to the VRE users.

Figure 1 shows the relevant components of the Blue-Cloud VRE and how the federation brings additional services and resources together.

¹ https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-core-1_0.html

Figure 1 – Logical view of the Federation in the VRE

Users access the VLabs and services of the Blue-Cloud VRE Gateway, available at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/>. These are built on top of the Blue-Cloud VRE Core Services. The main integration point for the federation is by deploying the Analytics Computing Framework components, which includes JupyterHub², Galaxy³ and Analytics Engines, on the available federated resources. Direct access to the resources is not offered, these are always delivered through higher abstraction layers that facilitate their usage and integration in the VRE.

The resources can be either OpenStack projects where the VRE operators can manage Virtual Machines or managed Kubernetes clusters that support the execution of container-based applications. For uniform deployment and facilitating the migration from one federated provider to another, for those Analytics Computing Framework components (JupyterHub and Galaxy) designed to run on Kubernetes, Kubernetes is deployed on top of the OpenStack resources. This architecture allows for the expansion of the resources available to the Blue-Cloud VRE on multiple providers without changing the provider configuration nor imposing additional requirements on them while keeping the user experience consistent across the federation.

² <https://jupyter.org/hub>

³ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

Third party services are integrated using IAM integration without entering into the details of the underlying supporting infrastructure. Optionally these services can be deployed on the available OpenStack or Kubernetes resources after agreement with the VRE operators.

1.2. Implementation Strategies within the VRE

1.2.1. Federation of Kubernetes providers

Kubernetes is a portable, extensible, open-source platform for managing containerized workloads and services, that facilitates both declarative configuration and automation. Kubernetes can be considered the de-facto standard for container-based application management, thanks to its wide support for running on every major cloud provider and on premises setups. Kubernetes abstracts the underlying hardware in a uniform way, making it possible to deploy applications on disparate infrastructures without any changes.

The Analytics Computing Framework deployment on Kubernetes requires:

- Kubernetes version 1.23 or later.
- Support for the Kubernetes Ingress objects is provided. An ingress allows mapping external traffic to different backends based on rules.
- Support for the creation of shared volumes that can be accessed by several pods (a pod is the basic scheduling unit for Kubernetes, and is composed of one or more containers with shared computing, network and storage resources). NFS is a possible technology for supporting these volumes.
- Allow the usage of fuse⁴ for mounting the user’s workspace.

1.2.1.1. Dataspaces

Each of the available clusters from different e-infrastructure providers will support one or multiple VLabs. Before deploying the services, the Blue-Cloud VRE operators will create a set of dataspaces volumes, depending on the VREs to be supported. These are available as a Kubernetes Persistent Volume Claim and will be available for all the applications running on the cluster and supporting the VRE. The below shows a sample definition of a 1TB dataspaces volume for Blue-Cloud:

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: blue-cloud-dataspaces
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteMany
  resources:
```

⁴ <https://github.com/libfuse/libfuse>

```
requests:
  storage: 1000Gi
storageClassName: nfs-client
volumeMode: Filesystem
```

Any application running on the Kubernetes cluster will be able to access the volumes to provide a shared space where users belonging to a given VLab can contribute to.

Figure 2 – Dataspace volume mounting by VRE services

1.2.1.2. Federation through JupyterHub

JupyterHub⁵ is a multi-user environment managing access to computational environments and resources within a user-friendly interface. Originally designed to support the execution of Jupyter⁶, its customisation options allow for the on-demand execution of a large set of interactive applications running on various types of infrastructure, from personal laptops to HPC clusters.

JupyterHub architecture is shown in Figure 3. JupyterHub is a set of processes that together, provide a single-user Jupyter Notebook server for each person in a group. There are three main subsystems:

⁵ <https://jupyter.org/hub>

⁶ <https://jupyter.org/>

Figure 3 –JupyterHub in Blue-Cloud-2026

- Hub: manages user accounts, authentication, and coordinates Single User Notebook Servers. Different authenticators control access to JupyterHub and the Spawner controls how JupyterHub starts the individual notebook server for each user.
- Proxy: the public-facing part of JupyterHub that uses a dynamic proxy to route HTTP requests to the Hub and Single User Notebook Servers.
- Single-User Notebook Server: a dedicated, single-user, Jupyter Notebook server is started for each user on the system when the user logs in.

In the case of Blue-Cloud, the JupyterHub is customized with a D4Science authenticator and a D4Science spawner. Both are available in GitHub⁷.

The D4Science authenticator performs authentication of the users with the D4Science IAM. Besides authentication, it also performs authorization by checking the user membership to the VREs and will dynamically configure the availability of environments and dataspace for the users by querying the D4Science Information System. The D4Science spawner creates Single-User Notebooks servers on Kubernetes ensuring the configuration of the access to the appropriate dataspace.

JupyterHub is used to manage two types of environments:

⁷ <https://github.com/EGI-federation/egi-notebooks-hub>

- Native Jupyter Notebooks with Python, Julia and R, with different library environments as requested by the VRE users.
- Proxied applications through the Jupyter server proxy extension⁸, such as RStudio and Pluto.jl. This extension allows for any interactive application that can be containerised and that uses HTTP to be accessed as part of the Jupyter session without any modification.

New applications can be easily added given the following constraints:

- Applications need to be packaged as a set of docker containers running as non-root user. Several containers can be run in parallel (i.e. sidecar containers).
- Alongside the application, the main docker container for the application must have the JupyterHub, Jupyter and Jupyter-server-proxy python libraries installed. Within a working python environment, this can be achieved with:
 - `pip install jupyterhub jupyter jupyter-server-proxy`
- A configuration for jupyter-server-proxy so the application can be started when the container is started as described in the documentation⁹.

JupyterHub takes care of starting an instance of the applications for every individual user, ensuring they run isolated without interfering with each other. The dataspace is mounted and made available to applications in the expected location.

When a user logs into the system a Server Options page will be shown (see Figure 4) so the user can select the most appropriate for his/her needs. The list of options is dynamically created by querying the D4Science Information System and checking the permissions received from IAM upon authentication.

⁸ <https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyter-server-proxy>

⁹ <https://jupyter-server-proxy.readthedocs.io/en/latest/server-process.html>

Figure 4 – Server Options

Each JupyterHub available for a given user on a VLab is easily accessible via the top menu of the VLab (Figure 5). For each of the e-infrastructure there is a Start (to create the Notebook server) and a Stop (to stop a running Notebook server) so users can easily access and manage resources from different infrastructures in a seamless way.

Figure 5 – JupyterLab menu in the VRE

Other non-Jupyter applications can be made available in a similar way; for example, RStudio menu will show Start and Stop options for each of the available e-infrastructures. From the deployment point of view there is no need to have separate JupyterHub instances and RStudio and JupyterLab are managed in the same way, only differing on the set of Server Options shown to the user which will be determined by the context of the user when reaching the hub available from the Information System and the information received from IAM.

Figure 6 – RStudio Server Options

1.2.1.3. Federation through Galaxy

Galaxy is a scientific workflow platform that aims to make computational workflows accessible to research scientists that do not have computer programming or systems administration experience. Although it was initially developed for genomics research, it is largely domain agnostic and is now used as a general workflow management system. Galaxy is a complex web-based application mostly written in python with a web-based user interface. With a drag and drop interface, users can execute single tools or a set of tools in a workflow from the browser. Galaxy can use a wide variety of backends for executing those tools, ensuring that the tools are invoked with the right input and that the output is made back available in the platform. In the case of the Blue-Cloud VRE, Galaxy is deployed using (1) a main Galaxy server pod that runs the Galaxy code for managing the platform; (2) a shared PVC where the data files are persisted and shared between all the Galaxy jobs, and (3) Galaxy tools job that are spawned whenever the users triggers the execution of a workflow. These jobs share access to the Galaxy PVC so they can easily read input data and produce output data. Galaxy takes care of ensuring each job can only access the files it is entitled to access. With this architecture, Galaxy can scale to run as many jobs in parallel as resources are available in the Kubernetes cluster as each job can run independently.

1.2.2. Federation of OpenStack

OpenStack is an open-source cloud computing platform used to build and manage public and private cloud infrastructures. It provides a set of software tools to help organizations set up and manage cloud services like computing, networking, storage, and more, all within their own data centres or across a distributed environment. OpenStack essentially provides the infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) layer for cloud computing. In the case of Blue-Cloud, OpenStack is used to start Virtual Machines where the Analytics Computing Framework components can be deployed. There are three main ways OpenStack is exploited within the VRE:

1. Deployment of JupyterHub/Galaxy and other Kubernetes-based applications. In this case a Kubernetes cluster is set up on top of the OpenStack. This allows for a uniform management of the applications and easy migration between providers.
2. Deployment of the Cloud Compute Platform (CCP). CCP uses containers through Docker Swarm, which can be executed on top of generic VMs delivered by OpenStack.
3. Deployment of third-party applications directly on VMs. Especially suited for the “lift and shift” approach of moving applications to the cloud, where the application is migrated from an on-premises setup to a cloud infrastructure with minimal changes or re-architecting. The application is packaged as a VM and executed on OpenStack without additional changes.

1.2.2.1. Setup of Kubernetes clusters on OpenStack

If a provider does not deliver a managed Kubernetes ready to be used by D4Science, the Blue-Cloud VRE operators can set-up a working Kubernetes cluster on top of OpenStack or bare-metal resources. The hardware requirements are as follows:

1. One master node with at least 2 cores, 8GB of RAM and 100 GB of disk space. The master should not be exposed to the public internet.
2. One NFS node with at least 2 cores, 8GB of RAM and disk space to host the shared dataspace and user homes. The disk space will depend on the amount and size of dataspace and the number of users to support in this cluster.
3. A set of worker nodes with at least 8 cores, 16 GB of RAM and 500GB of disk space (disk space is used to store the container images) where the actual workloads will be run. One of these nodes (called ingress node) should be accessible through ports 80 and 443 to the public internet so it can be reached by the users.

A Terraform¹⁰ configuration template for creating these nodes on OpenStack providers is available in GitHub¹¹.

Once the nodes are available, they are configured with ansible, which will take care of:

- Configure ssh access for the operators of the Kubernetes cluster
- Installing and configuring Kubernetes on the available nodes
- Installing and configuring NFS so it can be used for the creation of the volumes
- Installing a NGINX-based ingress for exposing the applications installed on top of Kubernetes, and assigning to it the public IP of the ingress node
- Installing cert-manager for the automated retrieval of SSL certificates for the applications running on Kubernetes
- Installing prometheus and grafana for the monitoring of the nodes of the cluster

1.2.3. Federation through CCP

The Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) is natively designed in a distributed and federation oriented way. As shown in the following figure showing its logical architecture, CCP is composed of its functional core and a set of Controllers that interface CCP with its execution infrastructures. The CCP Core runs as a Docker stack on the D4Science Docker swarm cluster hosted on ISTI OpenStack infrastructure. The Controllers are components that logically act on behalf of CCP but can be deployed in different ways depending on the communication patterns they use for interacting with the controlled execution infrastructure.

¹⁰ <https://www.terraform.io/>

¹¹ <https://github.com/EGI-Federation/notebooks/tree/main/template/terraform>

Figure 7 – CCP Logical Architecture

The rationale behind this architectural design is that it must be possible to run methods and algorithms on CCP from as many other platforms as possible and it must be possible to incrementally federate as many heterogeneous execution infrastructures as possible.

In order to provide different execution infrastructures several controllers have been built and others are ongoing or possible candidates as shown in the following picture.

Figure 8 – Developed, planned and possible CCP execution infrastructures

Docker-swarm controller enables Docker swarm clusters to become execution infrastructures for methods packed in Docker containers. The native D4Science Production and Development clusters are the primary, native execution infrastructures of CCP. In the case of the natively supported infrastructures the controller is deployed tightly coupled with CCP core on the same resources.

In addition, a plain **Docker controller** has been developed in order to allow the adoption of personal PCs and laptops as execution infrastructures. This is especially useful for onboarding developers of CCP itself or to verify the possibility to run GPU based methods. Instances of these controllers are usually deployed locally onto the user’s hardware.

A **Galaxy controller** has been added in order to be able to run Galaxy tools and workflows as CCP methods. This controller can be deployed on D4Science resources and it interacts with the Galaxy instance it controls through Galaxy REST API calls. The controller has been tested with Galaxy instances provided by D4Science and with usegalaxy.eu.

Currently, the D4Science developers are implementing **Kubernetes controllers**. These controllers will be able to run CCP methods encapsulated inside Docker containers also on Kubernetes controlled resources. Kubernetes infrastructures will be made available natively by D4Science as described in earlier sections.

During meetings with Blue-Cloud2026 partners, other ideas have emerged and there are plans to at least evaluate and document possible implementations for running CCP controlled methods on top of more HPC oriented platforms such as **Singularity** clusters or **SLURM** managed clusters.

As described before, another idea of federating CCP is based on the possibility to run CCP methods from as many platforms as possible. This interoperability is possible by the design of a standards based REST API (OGC Processes 1.1) to request method execution. Any authorized user or software can interact with CCP in order to get access to the list of methods, request their execution and monitor it.

Supporting tools like code generators have been made available to further ease the work for users.

It's now possible to run CCP methods from Bash, Python, Julia and R code or from platforms like JupyterHub and R-Studio.

A generic CCP method executor has been integrated in Galaxy in order to execute any CCP method by simply providing a request data structure (that can be easily generated with a click). In addition, CCP methods can be exported and imported into Galaxy instances as specialized tools on their own and then become part of workflows.

Figure 9 – CCP methods in Galaxy

Generic Galaxy 24 Tool

A Generic Galaxy 24 tool execution

Inputs

- * Runtime
The image of the runtime to use for method execution. This depends on the infrastructure specific protocol for interacting with registries.
- * Tool ID
The ID of the tool to execute on the Galaxy 24 infrastructure
- * Tool version
The version of the tool to be executed
- * API key
Your API key created for the Galaxy 24 infrastructure
- * Resource type
Either tool or Workflow
- * ID of history
The id of a history otherwise a new one will be created
- * Annotations for execution
The value of this parameter will be associated as annotation to the execution

Figure 10 – Running a Galaxy tool from CCP

Another activity that has been carried out is the integration of HEU **iImagine project**¹² containers for AI based algorithms. Two methods have been integrated (deephdc/deep-oc-plants-classification-tf and ai4oshub/ai4os-image-classification-tf) and a workflow for partially automating the process has been implemented.

¹² <https://www.imagine-ai.eu/>

Figure 11 – iMagine methods integrated in CCP

2. Federated infrastructures

This section describes the federated infrastructures currently integrated into the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and the operational status achieved in this second release. Building on the federation architecture and implementation approaches presented in Section 1, the following subsections provide a detailed overview of the concrete e-infrastructure providers and services that contribute computing capacity, storage, specialised processing capabilities and advanced data services to the Blue-Cloud ecosystem.

Compared to the first release (D5.3), this second release significantly expands the federation landscape. While the earlier phase focused primarily on establishing baseline computing federation across major cloud and OpenStack providers, the present release extends the federation and reports the successful integration of integration of SOCIB services as a semantically enriched service layer and the deployment of Beacon technology as a federated high-performance data subsetting infrastructure. These additions extend the scope of federation beyond computing resources to include knowledge services and data lake capabilities that directly support WorkBench analytics and VLab workflows. These represent the main federation milestones achieved during this reporting period and demonstrate the scalability and extensibility of the Blue-Cloud VRE model.

2.1. Google Cloud Platform

Google Cloud Platform (GCP) is a suite of cloud computing services offered by Google. It provides a wide range of infrastructure, platform, and software services for computing, storage, networking, machine learning, and more. Google Kubernetes Engine (GKE) is a managed Kubernetes service provided by GCP that simplifies the deployment, management, and scaling of containerized applications. GKE removes much of the operational overhead of managing Kubernetes clusters by automating tasks such as cluster upgrades, health monitoring, and security patching.

In the context of Blue-Cloud, two GKE Kubernetes clusters are available for the federation of resources in the VRE: one for production usage and a second one for testing and development purposes. These clusters are set with auto-scaling, so they automatically scale the number of nodes in a cluster and dynamically allocate resources based on workload demands. Figure 12 shows the GCP dashboard for the production environment.

Figure 12 – GCP Console

In order to deploy Jupyterhub in GKE, some of the configuration was tuned to adapt to the new environment:

- User applications (the single-user servers) are created in different Kubernetes namespaces for better control of the consumption of resources as each namespace can be configured independently with specific quotas and limits.
- Applications are exposed through the native GKE ingress and load balancer instead of the NGINX-Ingress used in other deployments.
- Dataspaces are created on Google Filestore, a fully managed network-attached storage system that can be attached as volumes in GKE Kubernetes clusters.
- Container images for the applications are stored in Google Artifact Registry for faster access from the nodes of the cluster (see Figure 13)

The screenshot shows the Google Cloud Artifact Registry interface. At the top, the breadcrumb navigation indicates the path: europe-west4-docker.pkg.dev > d4science-prod-vre-prj > d4science-prod-images. The 'Repository Details' section shows the format as 'Docker' and the type as 'Standard'. Below this is a table of images with columns for Name, Connection, Created, and Updated. The table lists several images, including 'hub', 'rstudio-d4science', and various 'single-user' images.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name ↑	Connection	Created	Updated
<input type="checkbox"/>	hub	–	Jan 31, 2024	Feb 20, 2024
<input type="checkbox"/>	rstudio-d4science	–	Apr 26, 2024	8 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-d4science	–	Feb 6, 2024	9 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-pluto-d4science	–	Oct 24, 2024	Oct 24, 2024
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-r-d4science	–	Feb 7, 2024	9 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-sobigdata	–	Feb 6, 2024	9 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-sobigdata-aaai24	–	Feb 20, 2024	Feb 20, 2024

Figure 13 – Google Artifact Registry

Currently the production cluster supports a JupyterHub installation and two Galaxy installations for Blue-Cloud and the Marine Omics VLab. This cluster is configured to use a node pool where each node has 20 CPU cores and 70 GB of RAM with autoscaling so new nodes will be created on the fly whenever the load. Figure 14 shows the list of nodes available in the pool.

The screenshot shows the Google Cloud Platform console for a Kubernetes cluster. The cluster name is 'd4science-prod-vre-gke-cluster'. There are two warning messages: one about Pod Disruption Budget (PDB) for 0 Pod evictions, and another about readiness probes for a StatefulSet. The 'NODES' tab is selected, showing a table of node pools and a table of individual nodes.

Name	Status	Version	Number of nodes	Machine type	Image type	Autoscaling	Default IPv4 Pod IP address range
d4science-prod-vre-gke-nodepool	Ok	1.30.5-gke.1443001	3 (1 per zone)	custom-20-73728	Container-Optimized OS with containerd (cos_containerd)	1 - 30 nodes per zone	10.250.0.0/17

Name	Status	CPU requested	CPU allocatable	Memory requested	Memory allocatable	Storage requested	Storage allocatable
gke-d4science-prod-v-d4science-prod-v-88f17371-3790	Ready	1.1 CPU	19.88 CPU	1.82 GB	69.17 GB	0 B	0 B
gke-d4science-prod-v-d4science-prod-v-c61604de-syrc	Ready	766 mCPU	19.88 CPU	1.67 GB	69.17 GB	0 B	0 B
gke-d4science-prod-v-d4science-prod-v-dd26e776-mfx1	Ready	762 mCPU	19.88 CPU	1.3 GB	69.17 GB	0 B	0 B

Figure 14 – Node pools in production cluster

2.2. EGI Cloud Compute - INFN Bari

EGI Cloud Compute is a multi-cloud service that offers access to OpenStack providers to run Virtual Machines on demand with complete control over computing resources. EGI Cloud Compute gives you the ability to deploy and scale virtual machines on-demand. It offers guaranteed computational resources in a secure and isolated environment with standard API access, without the overhead of managing physical servers. INFN-Bari is one of the EGI's resource centres that contribute computing power, storage, and other resources to the EGI Cloud Compute Service.

Blue-Cloud-2026 has established a Service Level Agreement between EGI and the project to define the provision and support of the services listed in the Table below.

Resource Center	Cloud Compute	Online Storage
INFN-Bari	32 vCPU cores, 32 GB RAM, Floating IPs available, 200 GB of SSD storage	25 TB

Table 1 – EGI Cloud Compute allocation at INFN-Bari

These resources are used to deploy a webODV instance for Blue-Cloud VRE users with access to large ocean datasets from the global Argo program and the SeaDataNet infrastructure. Figure 15 shows the OpenStack overview dashboard for the allocated resources at the provider.

Figure 15 – OpenStack dashboard at INFN-Bari

A single VM with all the available capacity runs webODV through Docker compose at the site and available as part of the VRE offer as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16 – webODV in Blue-Cloud Lab

2.3. SOCIB

The SOCIB integration represents a service-level federation within the Blue-Cloud VRE. Unlike the infrastructure-centric integrations described in D5.3 (Kubernetes/OpenStack deployments), SOCIB contributes a semantically enriched service layer based on Science Knowledge Graphs and maDMP interoperability. The service is hosted at SOCIB but federated into the Blue-Cloud VRE through IAM integration and API interoperability, thus aligning with the federation principles defined in Section 1.

Background: From JERICO-S3 and OSTrails to Blue-Cloud2026

The SOCIB contribution to Blue-Cloud2026 builds directly on the experience and lessons learned in JERICO-S3, OSTrails, and earlier Blue-Cloud activities. In particular, JERICO-S3 explored the use of Science Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) to integrate information from multiple heterogeneous sources related to marine observations and services. The SKG, together with a dedicated API, was implemented using RDF technologies and operated on the Datarmor infrastructure, while assessment notebooks were developed and executed within the JERICO-CORE VLab in Blue-Cloud.

OSTrails extends this work by advancing interoperable, machine-actionable data management practices and aligning SKG and maDMP approaches with EOSC and RDA standards. While the project focuses on connecting data management plans, FAIR assessment frameworks, and knowledge graphs for multiple domains, we apply this approach in a pilot on glider data management as a concrete ENVRI community use case, supporting the effort for cross-domain interoperability.

This work highlighted several structural challenges: including limited standardization of metadata parameters, inconsistencies across sources, insufficient use of persistent identifiers (PIDs), and the consequent difficulty of recognizing and matching the same digital objects (DOs) across catalogues and infrastructures. Additional challenges included identifying community-specific resources and contextualizing data flows within specific programmes or initiatives, while the lack of a shared, interoperable data model limited the integration of heterogeneous data sources and alignment with other SKGs and broader EOSC and ENVRI efforts.

Operationally, the JERICO-S3 SKG relied on largely automated ingestion and synchronization mechanisms, including detection of updates at source. However, experience showed a strong need for human-in-the-loop curation, supported by dedicated tools, to clean, consolidate, and validate graph content. These limitations were further evidenced by the initial assessments of existing digital objects that were carried out in JERICO-CORE Vlab that revealed metadata gaps and errors in upstream sources, demonstrating the value of SKGs as assessment and feedback mechanisms for data providers.

JERICO-S3 also explored the assessment of software resources, showing a clear evolution in software development practices during the project lifecycle (D6.9 deliverable¹³). These activities identified the need for: (i) a robust, interoperable data model; (ii) editors for SKGs and maDMPs; and (iii) integrated assessment frameworks.

Use case demonstrator: JERICO-S3 TAs

The primary use case demonstrated in Blue-Cloud focuses on the JERICO-S3 Transnational Access (TA) activities, using the infrastructure to retrospectively assess project impact and compliance with data management requirements. Although the assessment is performed after the formal end of JERICO-S3, it serves as a realistic demonstration of how the service can be used operationally in future projects and infrastructures.

Concretely, the use case evaluates whether data generated by TA projects:

- follows the data management plan defined by JERICO-S3 (D6.12 deliverable²¹⁴);
- is correctly distributed to relevant data aggregators.

As an initial strategy, the assessment focused on TA glider missions operated by SOCIB, for which detailed operational, metadata, and dissemination information is readily available. These missions will serve as a controlled and well-understood subset to validate the assessment workflow and demonstrate the value of combining SKGs, maDMPs, and FAIR assessments within Blue-Cloud. In a subsequent phase, we aim to invite the broader JERICO-S3 community to include additional TA, enabling a more comprehensive evaluation of how project outputs adhere to the JERICO-S3 data management plan.

By extending the assessments across missions and infrastructures, the use case will highlight the role of European data aggregators (EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service, and SeaDataNet) in supporting the dissemination, visibility, and reuse of data generated by EC-funded projects. Furthermore, for the JERICO community, these assessments provide tangible evidence of data management compliance and impact, supporting ESFRI-related activities and applications by demonstrating alignment with European standards, FAIR principles, and long-term sustainability expectations.

Service overview

¹³ https://www.jerico-ri.eu/download/jerico-s3_deliverables/DL6.9_JERICO-S3_D6.9_E-Library-contributions.pdf

¹⁴ https://www.jerico-ri.eu/download/jerico-s3_deliverables/DL6.12_JERICO-S3_D6.12_Final-data-management-plan.pdf

In Blue-Cloud2026, we deliver a federated service that integrates the three interoperable frameworks defined in the context of the OSTRails project:

- the Science Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) for representing and linking digital objects, actors, processes, and initiatives;
- the machine-actionable Data Management Plan Interoperability Framework (maDMP-IF) to formally describe data management plans and connect them to concrete digital objects and data flows;
- the FAIR Interoperability Framework (FAIR-IF) to enable systematic assessments of FAIRness and process compliance.

The service is offered within the Blue-Cloud infrastructure as a federated component hosted by SOCIB and integrated into the Blue-Cloud VRE. It is initially made available through the JERICO-CORE VLab for testing and validation in the context of the use case described above. This initial integration serves to demonstrate both the value of the service and its role as a prototype implementation of how a federated service can be embedded within a Blue-Cloud VLab. While the current deployment targets the JERICO-CORE VLab, it is designed as a reusable integration pattern, illustrating how other V Labs could adopt and integrate the service in the future as it matures and becomes more broadly available.

The technical foundation of the service is provided by the OSTRails SKG and maDMP data models, originally developed to support the ENVRI/JERICO OSTRail thematic pilot for glider data management. These models are aligned with RDA recommendations and EOSC interoperability principles, ensuring compatibility with the ENVRI ecosystem and, in particular, with the marine and ocean glider communities. In Blue-Cloud2026, these data models are adopted as the reference for the JERICO-SKG, guaranteeing interoperability across infrastructures. The service further incorporates mechanisms to link digital objects to specific initiatives and programmes through maDMPs, enabling explicit representation of data flows, responsibilities and related assets (e.g. data endpoints).

Building on this foundation, we have developed within WP5:

- an SKG editor that supports manual creation, curation, and cleaning of graph entities, addressing limitations identified in fully automated approaches;
- a mechanism to ingest maDMP descriptions into the SKG;
- a dashboard to evaluate the dissemination of JERICO-S3 Transnational Access (TA) outputs into the main data aggregators.

In addition, integration points for FAIR assessments will be implemented based on FAIR-IF concepts and tools emerging from OSTrails. This will allow progressive incorporation of more advanced assessment capabilities as the FAIR-IF matures and is integrated into Blue-Cloud. Some envisioned assessment functionalities will extend beyond the formal end of the Blue-Cloud2026 project. As the FAIR-IF continues to evolve within OSTrails, in close synergy with OSTrails national and thematic pilots, improvements to the SKG-IF, maDMP-IF, and FAIR-IF can be directly exploited by Blue-Cloud.

As a concrete instantiation of this approach, we are planning in the context of OSTrails that FAIR assessments will evaluate compliance with Ocean Glider community standards (OG1.0), including the completeness and correctness of mandatory metadata fields. The resulting assessment will demonstrate how SKGs and maDMPs can be combined to trace data flows from projects to repositories and onward to aggregators, while providing measurable indicators of data quality, interoperability, and FAIRness.

Finally, we plan to explore the integration of maDMP editors being developed and refined within OSTrails, which are interoperable by design. These editors will facilitate the creation of maDMPs by Blue-Cloud V Labs using the appropriate data models, ensuring that maDMPs can be automatically ingested and interpreted by the Science Knowledge Graph (SKG) for evaluation purposes. The SKG itself is implemented as part of the SKG Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) and exposes an API compliant with the interoperability standards defined in OSTrails, enabling consistent access, integration, and reuse across infrastructures and services.

In general, there will be a continuous evolution of this federated service in the context of OSTrails beyond the project lifetime Blue-Cloud2026. Therefore, Blue-Cloud will benefit from these improvements and can maximize long-term impact for the marine community and strengthen alignment with EOSC and ENVRI ecosystems.

Technical implementation

The [SKG-Editor](#) is a web application written in Python 3.13. It uses the [FastAPI](#) module which itself is based on the lightweight ASGI (asynchronous server gateway interface) framework/toolkit [Starlette](#) acting as the server backend. The backend connects to a [neo4j graph database cloud instance](#) via its [Python driver](#).

The frontend provides the user with dedicated HTML forms to view and edit nodes of the science knowledge graph instance or to search public databases for metadata to import into the graph. The implementation allows searching in and importing from the [EDMO](#) and [ORCID](#) databases for metadata describing '[agents](#)'. The integration of additional external data sources is envisioned for future releases.

Except for the index page of the SKG-Editor, all resources require authentication. In the current deployment, user sessions are authenticated through the [Blue-Cloud Identity and Access Management \(IAM\)](#) service using the [OpenID Connect](#) authorization flow, enabling seamless access from within the VRE

without additional credentials. This approach also eliminates the need of maintaining a dedicated user database as part of the deployment.

Figure 17 – SKG Editor architecture

The landing page of the SKG-Editor provides the user with an overview of the available endpoints as well as links to the corresponding SKG-IF documentation to each of the data models (see screenshot below):

Science Knowledge Graph Editor

Person Nodes
 Agent entity of subtype 'person'.
 Please see [Data Model](#) for detailed information.
[List All](#) [Import from ORCID](#) [Create New](#)

Organisation Nodes
 Agent entity of subtype 'organisation'.
 Please see [Data Model](#) for detailed information.
[List All](#) [Import from EDMO](#) [Create New](#)

Research Product Nodes
 Scientific data, software or literature.
 Please see [Data Model](#) for detailed information.
[List All](#) [Create New](#)

Grant Nodes
 Funds provided by a funding body to an agent.
 Please see [Data Model](#) for detailed information.
[List All](#) [Create New](#)

Venue Nodes
 Journals or similar publishing gateways for 'research products'.
 Please see [Data Model](#) for detailed information.
[List All](#) [Create New](#)

Data Source Nodes
 Service or platform where a 'research product' is made accessible.
 Please see [Data Model](#) for detailed information.
[List All](#) [Create New](#)

Graph Database Summary

Total Node Count	86
Total Relationship Count	76
Data Management Plans	0
Persons	1
Organisations	1
Research Products	2
Grants	1
Venues	1
Data Sources	1
External Identifiers	18

Data Management Plan — validation and import tool
 This endpoint allows for the validation of DMPs in JSON format and their subsequent import into the graph database.
 Open with a [DMP example](#)
 Open as [empty validation form](#)

Figure 18 – SKG Landing page

Node Creation and Editing

Example view of an entity of type 'organisation'.

SOCIB Seismic Islands Control Observing and Forecasting System
SIGN OUT

Node Viewer — Organisation RELOAD DATASET

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Name Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
Short Name CNR
Other Names National Research Council, Conseil National de la Recherche
Website <https://www.cnr.it/>
Country IT
Organisation Type research
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:e621133d-0174-41ca-b7e0-bed7e3233f44
 Created 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000
 Last Modified 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000

Associated Affiliates

- [Andrea Mannocci](#)

Associated External Identifier Nodes

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Scheme ROR
Value 04zaypm56
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:8c1b5466-c7d4-44d8-9856-8229c3cd80b1
 Created 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000
 Last Modified 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000

+ CREATE NEW

Scheme

Value

Figure 19 – SKG View of entity

Associated external identifiers of the organisation can be added, edited or removed directly via the integrated sub-forms.

Node Viewer — Organisation RELOAD DATASET

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Name Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
Short Name CNR
Other Names National Research Council, Conseil National de la Recherche
Website <https://www.cnr.it/>
Country IT
Organisation Type research
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:e621133d-0174-41ca-b7e0-bed7e3233f44
 Created 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000
 Last Modified 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000

Associated Affiliates

- [Andrea Mannocci](#)

Associated External Identifier Nodes

SAVE CHANGES
DISCARD CHANGES

Scheme ARXIV

Value

Local Identifier urn:uuid:8c1b5466-c7d4-44d8-9856-8229c3cd80b1

+ CREATE NEW

Scheme ARXIV

Value

Figure 20 – SKG Associated external identifiers.

Node Viewer — Organisation RELOAD DATASET

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Name Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
Short Name CNR
Other Names National Research Council, Conseil National de la Recherche
Website <https://www.cnr.it/>
Country IT
Organisation Type research
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:621133d-0174-41ca-b7e0-bed7e3233f44
 Created 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000
 Last Modified 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000

Associated Affiliates

- [Andrea Mannocci](#)

Associated External Identifier Nodes

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Scheme ROR
Value 04zaypm56
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:8c1b5466-c7d4-44d8-9856-8229c3cd80b1
 Created 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000
 Last Modified 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000

CREATE NEW

Scheme

Value

Figure 21 – SKG Editing associated external identifiers.

Node Viewer — Organisation RELOAD DATASET

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Name Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
Short Name CNR
Other Names National Research Council, Conseil National de la Recherche
Website <https://www.cnr.it/>
Country IT
Organisation Type research
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:621133d-0174-41ca-b7e0-bed7e3233f44
 Created 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000
 Last Modified 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000

Associated Affiliates

- [Andrea Mannocci](#)

Associated External Identifier Nodes

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Scheme ROR
Value 04zaypm56
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:8c1b5466-c7d4-44d8-9856-8229c3cd80b1
 Created 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000
 Last Modified 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Scheme URL
Value www.example.com
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:644f62f9-64c3-4baa-9a65-a84526b4abc7
 Created 2026-01-30T09:05:01+0000
 Last Modified 2026-01-30T09:05:01+0000

CREATE NEW

Scheme

Value

Figure 22 – SKG Adding an additional associated external identifier.

Node Editor — Organisation

✓ SAVE CHANGES
✗ DISCARD CHANGES

Name	<input type="text" value="Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche"/>
Short Name	<input type="text" value="CNR"/>
Other Names	<input type="text" value="National Research Council, Conseil National de la Recherche"/>
Website	<input type="text" value="https://www.cnr.it/"/>
Country Code	<input type="text" value="IT"/>
Type	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; min-height: 100px;"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> archive company education facility government healthcare nonprofit funder <li style="background-color: #f0f0f0;">research unspecified </div>
Local Identifier	urn:uuid:e621133d-0174-41ca-b7e0-bed7e3233f44
Created	2025-11-20T12:34:37.172000000+00:00
Modified	2025-11-20T12:34:37.172000000+00:00

Associated Affiliates

- [Andrea Mannocci](#)

Associated External Identifier Nodes

✎ EDIT NODE
✗ DELETE NODE

Scheme ROR
Value 04zaypm56
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:8c1b5466-c7d4-44d8-9856-8229c3cd80b1
 Created 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000
 Last Modified 2025-11-20T12:34:37+0000

➕ CREATE NEW

Scheme

Value

Figure 23 – SKG Editing the data of the ‘organisation’ node itself.

Search and Import

The exemplary lookup of an ORCID record is shown in the following sequence of screenshots:

Import — Person

Search and import persons from the [Open Researcher and Contributor ID database](#)

ORCID

Given Name(s)

Family Name(s)

Limit Results

ORCID search for '0000-0001-9277-6938' successful.

Import — Person

	NAME	ORCID
<input checked="" type="radio"/>	dummy dummy	0000-0001-9277-6938

This is the prototype of the frontend of an application under active development. Appearance and editor functions are subject to change.

[urn:uuid:4c03306d-c080-4835-b4f0-5dcb7527fb55] AGENT dataset successfully created.

Node Viewer — Person RELOAD DATASET

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Name dummy dummy
Given Name dummy
Family Name dummy
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:4c03306d-c080-4835-b4f0-5dcb7527fb55
 Created 2026-01-30T09:16:33+0000
 Last Modified 2026-01-30T09:16:33+0000

Associated Affiliation Nodes

CREATE NEW

With

Start

End

Associated External Identifier Nodes

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Scheme ORCID
Value 0000-0001-9277-6938
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:3c8ed923-0104-4bcd-9c8d-16bfb9e92b8b
 Created 2026-01-30T09:16:33+0000
 Last Modified 2026-01-30T09:16:33+0000

CREATE NEW

Scheme

Value

Figure 24 – SKG Lookup of an ORCID record

When importing a record by looking up an external identifier, the identifier will be added to the imported record immediately.

As a second example, the search for keywords in the European Directory of Marine Institutions (EDMO) is showcased in the following screenshot sequence. In contrast to the lookup of a unique identifier which should yield exactly 0 or 1 results, the user will likely receive multiple results to choose from. Links to inspect the retrieved records are provided along with the results so the user can make an informed decision regarding which record to import.

Import — Organisation

Search and import organisations from the [European Directory of Marine Organisations](#)

PID

Name

Fuzzy Search

Case Sensitive Search

Limit Results

EDMO search for 'Aarhus University' yielded 10 datasets.

Import — Organisation

[→ IMPORT](#) [× NEW SEARCH](#)

NAME	PID
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5580
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University, Department of Bioscience	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5123
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University, Department of Bioscience, Arctic Environment	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/793
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University, Department of BioScience, Center for Geomicrobiology	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/2194
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University, Department of Bioscience, Freshwater Ecology	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/792
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University, Department of Bioscience, Marine Ecology Aarhus	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/746
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University, Department of Bioscience, Marine Ecology Roskilde	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/729
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University, Department of Bioscience, Wildlife Ecology and Biodiversity	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1103
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University, Department of Geoscience	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5581
<input type="radio"/> Aarhus University, Danish Centre for Environment and Energy	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/3037

[urn:uuid:9d01145d-4014-4627-8a5b-1c3b66dc1fbd] AGENT dataset successfully created.

Node Viewer — Organisation

RELOAD DATASET

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Name Aarhus University, Department of Bioscience, Marine Ecology Aarhus
Short Name
Other Names
Website <http://bios.au.dk/en/>
Country Denmark
Organisation Type
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:9d01145d-4014-4627-8a5b-1c3b66dc1fbd
 Created 2026-01-30T09:27:59+0000
 Last Modified 2026-01-30T09:27:59+0000

Associated Affiliates

ⓘ No affiliates found. Affiliations can be created through the [Person Node Editor](#).

Associated External Identifier Nodes

EDIT NODE
DELETE NODE

Scheme EDMO
Value <https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/746>
 Local Identifier urn:uuid:531949eb-2f49-4593-9758-00728a4ba1b7
 Created 2026-01-30T09:27:59+0000
 Last Modified 2026-01-30T09:27:59+0000

CREATE NEW

Scheme

Value

Figure 25 – Search for keywords in the European Directory of Marine Institutions (EDMO)

All endpoints allow for the creation of new datasets by the user. The following screenshots illustrate the creation of an example ‘data source’ entity in the graph. Restrictions integrated in the HTML forms ensure that mandatory attributes (according to the [data model documentation](#)) are provided by the user. Furthermore, the different input types assist with the cardinality of a given data field (single value vs. multiple values).

SOCIB Remote Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System Endpoint Overview SKG-IF Data Model SIGN OUT

Node Editor — Data Source

[+ CREATE NEW](#)

Name Example Data Source

Disciplines list of disciplines (separated by ; ')

Classification repository

Audience

- Global
- National
- Regional
- Institution
- Research Infrastructure
- e-Infrastructure

Research Product Type

- metadata
- research data
- literature
- software
- any

Nodes for identifiers, persistent identity systems, classifications, etc. can be associated after the data source node has been created in the graph database.

SOCIB Remote Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System Endpoint Overview SKG-IF Data Model SIGN OUT

Node Editor — Data Source

[+ CREATE NEW](#)

Name Example Data Source

Disciplines list of disciplines (separated by ; ')

Classification repository

Audience

- Global
- National
- Regional
- Institution
- Research Infrastructure
- e-Infrastructure

Research Product Type

- metadata
- research data
- literature
- software
- any

Please select an item in the list.

Nodes for identifiers, persistent identity systems, classifications, etc. can be associated after the data source node has been created in the graph database.

Figure 26 – Creation of new datasets

2.4. Beacon

The integration of Beacon represents a major evolution of the Blue-Cloud federation model. While D5.3 focused on federating computational infrastructures, Beacon extends federation to high-performance

data subsetting and harmonisation services. This enables scalable, parameter-level data access across BDIs and supports WorkBench-driven analytics workflows within the VRE. Beacon therefore strengthens Blue-Cloud alignment with EOSC principles by enabling federated, interoperable and performance-optimised data exploitation.

Introduction

The Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service (DD&AS) supports discovery and download of **predefined data objects**, which are documented with metadata records. A user then might retrieve tens of thousands of individual data sets that he/she has to process to retrieve the specific data that he/she is after. In addition to the DD&AS service, the Blue-Cloud2026 project has initiated developments to establish high-performance **sub-setting or slicing functionality** on major repositories, such as the Blue-Cloud Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs), but also on international repositories such as the World Ocean Database (WOD), which are relevant for complementary data sets. Sub-setting aims to work at the level of the data sets, and facilitate extracting specific parameters and values from the data sets, for instance all temperature observations with temperature value > 10 degrees in October 2020 between 50 and 100 metres depth. Deploying sub-setting functionality on major repositories enables the creation and maintenance of **data lakes** for specific parameters through regular extractions, which can be directly exploited by Blue-Cloud WorkBenches and VRE-based analytical workflows.

It was decided to adopt and further explore a new technology, Beacon, for which MARIS had developed a prototype. The technology showed great potential from the perspective of BDIs and Work Benches, as it promised to make it possible to slice through data files as managed by BDIs, querying for parameters, depth, location, time period, and possible other criteria, and to generate homogeneous result files which contain the selected values and associated metadata. A prerequisite for the subsetting is that it really should perform on millions of data sets as it would then allow a user to browse through the resulting data, for instance in a viewer using sliders for depth, parameters, dates in a comfortable pace without having to wait.

The analysis and decisions about the way forward have been documented in Deliverable **D2.4 -BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Concept and Specifications Report** (<https://zenodo.org/records/11124839>) - which was released early May 2024. It details the envisioned data lake configurations and also about the Beacon technology that is being adopted for powering the data lakes. Furthermore, it describes the implementation planning and related actions.

The specifications and vision from D2.4 have been given a follow-up in the following months. The related activities and achieved results are described in the Deliverable **D2.5 - Established BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Documentation Report** (<https://zenodo.org/records/15055775>). Moreover, this deliverable documents next steps planned to achieve full operational and robust data provision workflows

on which the WorkBench teams can build their targeted analyses for generating high-quality EOVS collections.

The underlying Deliverable reports on the latest developments and deployments of Beacon.

Beacon - High performance open source subsetting technology

Description of Beacon

Beacon is a high performance open source data lake designed for subsetting and storing large quantities of climate data. Beacon is written by MARIS from scratch in Rust and C and makes use of many new OS kernel APIs to enable its high performance. The goal of a Beacon data lake is to provide an easy-to-use, fast, reliable, and scalable solution for storing, processing, and querying large amounts of climate and marine environmental data.

Features of Beacon are:

- **Open Source (AGPLv3):** Beacon is available under the AGPLv3 free and open source software license (FOSS). Meaning that every component of Beacon is fully open source available without restrictions. Anyone can use it, read the source code and set up a Beacon instance. All of the technology behind Beacon is available via GitHub: <https://github.com/maris-development/beacon>
- **Direct and Powerful Subsetting:** Beacon facilitates on the fly subsetting of millions of datasets and responds within milliseconds. It enables subsetting using the following methods:
 - Range (min,max) filtering of every column/parameter
 - Equality Filtering
 - Polygon filtering
 - Filtering on metadata
- **Ease of Use:** The data lake provides a simple and intuitive REST API with swagger documentation, making it easy to store, process, and retrieve/query your data.
- **Cross Platform:** Support for the following platforms via Docker:
 - Linux
 - MacOS (x86/64 and arm64)
 - Windows
- **S3 Cloud Support:** Since version 1.3, Beacon has the ability to be deployed directly on top of existing S3 buckets. Allowing data that is stored inside those S3 buckets to be directly subsetted

from using Beacon. These datasets are transparently visible via the Beacon API allowing users to see the datasets stored inside the S3 Bucket accessible by Beacon. Every feature of Beacon works with both datasets stored locally or in an existing S3 Bucket.

- **Understands Every Data Dimensionality:** Beacon understands how dimensionality in data sets represents the data and thus doesn't require to harmonise or prepare datasets. Whether the dataset is 1-dimensional or 4-dimensional, Beacon understands it.
- **Data Harmonisation:** With Beacon, users are able to harmonise various parts of their datasets and build even more powerful products. Various parameters can be harmonised together or even converted between different units, all on the fly using Beacon. This can all be done within a Query using JSON or SQL.
- **Many Output Formats:** Beacon can create a single harmonised output in many different formats such as:
 - Streaming Arrow IPC
 - NetCDF (flat and multi-dimensional)
 - ZARR (via Beacon Python SDK)
 - Parquet
 - GeoParquet
 - JSON
 - GeoJSON
 - CSV
 - Arrow IPC
 - WebODV
- **Performance:** Beacon is designed with performance in mind. Subsetting from millions of observational data records within seconds can enable a new range of applications to be built.
- **Scalability:** The Beacon data lake is designed to be highly scalable, allowing to store and process terabytes of data without sacrificing performance.
- **Union Queries:** With Beacon, it is possible to run union queries which enables users to run multiple individual queries at once and combine the results of those individual queries into a single aggregated and harmonised result file.
- **Federated Queries:** Using federated queries, it is possible to run a query against another Beacon instance instead of just the one you're running the query against. In combination with union

queries, this would allow users to run multiple federated queries against various Beacon instances and produce a single harmonised output file to the user.

- **Integration with Existing File Formats:** Beacon also supports directly reading and subsetting from existing datasets stored in familiar scientific file formats such as, NetCDF, ZARR, Parquet, Beacon Binary Format and many others. This allows Beacon to be run on top of an existing collection of datasets and immediately provide a high-performance harmonized subsetting API.
- **Integration With Python:** Beacon can be queried using a Beacon Python SDK (software development kit). This enables Jupyter Notebooks to have tight integration directly with Beacon as it can provide suggestions to the users on which datasets and collections are available directly in their IDE (integrated development environment). This enables users to build highly detailed queries with hinting directly from Beacon itself on the query possibilities.

Beacon website: <https://beacon.maris.nl>

Detailed documentation: <https://maris-development.github.io/beacon>

Beacon Binary Format

The Beacon Binary Format is designed to deliver high-performance data access and small data size. This format provides efficient storage and retrieval of data using variables and dimensions, accompanied by attributes to store metadata. The Beacon Binary Format draws inspiration from existing formats like NetCDF but introduces improvements to achieve significantly faster performance and support for multiple readers simultaneously.

Many existing formats involve deserialization costs, which can be a performance bottleneck when dealing with large datasets. Additionally, compression techniques employed in some formats can introduce overhead and hinder data access speed. The Beacon Binary Format addresses these issues by eliminating deserialization costs and using performance focused compression algorithms while ensuring efficient data representation.

The Beacon Binary Format offers several key features that distinguish it from other formats and make it a desirable choice for high-performance data processing:

- **Zero Copy Deserialization Cost:** The Beacon Binary Format eliminates the need for deserialization, allowing for direct access to data without incurring performance penalties. This advantage is achieved by storing data in a format that is directly compatible with the target language, avoiding the need for conversion or parsing operations during data retrieval. This format is designed to

optimise data retrieval, resulting in improved performance, especially for large-scale datasets.

- **Small Data Size:** The Beacon Binary Format focuses on minimising data size through compression without losing any performance. By utilising a compact binary representation, it achieves reduced storage requirements, facilitating faster data transfer and reducing storage costs.
- **Variables and Dimensions:** The format adopts a flexible structure by employing variables and dimensions to organise and represent data. Variables allow for the storage of multi-dimensional arrays, while dimensions define the size and shape of these arrays. This structure offers versatility and facilitates the storage of complex data structures.
- **Metadata Storage using Attributes:** Metadata plays a crucial role in describing and providing additional context to the stored data. Beacon employs attributes to store metadata, enabling the association of descriptive information, annotations, and other relevant attributes with the variables or on a global level with the dataset. This feature enhances data interpretability and facilitates efficient data management.
- **Simultaneous Multiple Readers:** The Beacon Binary Format supports concurrent access by multiple readers. This capability allows for parallel processing and efficient distribution of computational tasks across multiple threads or systems, contributing to improved performance in scenarios involving high-volume data access.

NetCDF, a popular data format for scientific and geospatial data, shares similarities with the Beacon Binary Format. However, the Beacon Binary Format improves upon NetCDF in several ways:

- **Enhanced Performance:** By eliminating deserialization costs and using performance focused compression algorithms, the Beacon Binary Format achieves higher performance compared to NetCDF. These optimizations reduce data access latency and enable faster computation on the stored data.
- **Concurrent Readers:** Unlike NetCDF, which typically supports a single reader at a time, Beacon Binary Format allows for concurrent access by multiple readers. This feature is particularly advantageous in scenarios where parallel processing and distributed computing are crucial.
- **Dynamic Chunking:** Beacon Binary Format is able to create chunks of loaded datasets which will allow for even more efficient reading. Beacon Binary Format makes use of a method called, Relative Optimised Chunking, that chunks datasets based on its actual data contents, instead of the dimensions provided by the dataset. This means observations of a dataset will be chunked

into parts that are in close proximity to each other (Eg. in longitude, latitude, time and depth). This allows for more efficient data retrieval, as Beacon can just load in the chunks required instead of the entire data array for a variable (eg. temperature).

- **Arrow Arrays:** Beacon Binary Format uses the “Arrow” memory layout for storing multi-dimensional arrays. This is key due to many of the high-performance tools utilizing “arrow arrays” as their input to start computational operations (eg. Polars, DuckDB, DataFusion). By storing the arrays as “arrow arrays”, it allows other high-performance tools to directly use it as input without having to translate the internal memory layout, allowing us to build data pipelines without translation layers making it true “zero-cost”.
- **S3 Support:** Beacon Binary Format natively supports S3 via a Rust library called “object store”. This allows Beacon to read from Beacon Binary Format files stored in arbitrary S3 buckets without any performance degradation. Making a cloud-native solution with Beacon viable and even better scalable beyond what is possible in an on-premise environment.

Beacon Performance Indications

Beacon offers powerful query capabilities and can filter on ranges, polygons and metadata. To illustrate this a test was done by loading Beacon with an increasing number of NetCDF files for Temperature and Salinity as derived from the SeaDataNet CDI Data Discovery and Access service.

In total more than 2.5 Million NetCDF files were loaded into Beacon after which queries were performed. For this test an instance of Beacon was deployed on a relatively small server (8 cores and 32 GB RAM). This implies that even a modern laptop will give even better results, not to speak of fast computer clusters as available in the Blue-Cloud VRE (D4Science e-infrastructure). The following image gives the results of the test queries, which are very good and can be repeated with different queries without any extra effort.

PERFORMANCE

Figure 27 –WOD Performance of Beacon queries for case with increasing number of SeaDataNet NetCDF files loaded into Beacon instance

Beacon deployments for BDI data collections

As a result of the discussions between WP2 and WP3 WorkBench teams and the overall discussions at the STC meetings, two main use cases have been formulated.

- A number of Beacon instances, each for selected data from a specific BDI, and made available for all Blue-Cloud VRE users;
- Two Beacon instances for WorkBench 1 respectively WorkBench 2, merging and harmonising selected data from multiple BDIs, and with regular and controlled updating mechanism.

Monolithic Beacon instances configured for selected BDIs and data collections

Beacon deployments

Together with the WorkBench 1 and 2 teams a short list has been made of BDI data collections that are relevant as input for the generation of EOVs for Temperature & Salinity (T&S) (WorkBench 1) and Eutrophication (WorkBench 2). Developments have been undertaken by MARIS for configuring the Beacon software and deployments have been established of Beacon instances, first at the MARIS servers. Later, after thorough testing in particular by members of the WorkBench 1 and 2 teams, these monolithic Beacon instances have also been deployed at the Blue-Cloud VRE. The term ‘monolithic’ is used to indicate that the Beacon instance concerns one data collection or BDI.

BDI data collection	Beacon instance	WorkBench
CORA Profile data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001	beacon-cora-pr.maris.nl beacon-cora-pr.d4science.org	WB1
CORA Timeseries data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001	beacon-cora-ts.maris.nl beacon-cora-ts.d4science.org	WB1
Euro-Argo data, retrieved from S3 bucket	beacon-argo.maris.nl beacon-argo.d4science.org	WB1
SeaDataNet data collection, synced and retrieved via the existing CDI system	beacon-cdi.maris.nl beacon-seadatanet.d4science.org	WB1
World Ocean Database (WOD) actual depths, retrieved from ncei.noaa.gov	beacon-wod.maris.nl beacon-wod.d4science.org	WB1 + WB2

BDI data collection	Beacon instance	WorkBench
EMODnet Chemistry North East Atlantic Collection (subset of the complete collection) retrieved from EMODnet Chemistry WebODV (Eutrophication_Atlantic_profiles_2023_unrestricted.odv)	beacon-emod-chem.maris.nl beacon-emodnet-chemistry.d4science.org	WB2
BGC data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_BGC_DISCRETE_MY_013_046	beacon-cmems.maris.nl beacon-bgc.d4science.org	WB2

Table 2 – Overview of deployed monolithic Beacon instances

World Ocean Database as example of beacon deployments

The World Ocean Database (WOD) is a comprehensive collection of oceanographic data developed and maintained by the National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC) and the World Data Service for Oceanography. It provides a globally integrated and consistent dataset of oceanographic parameters, including temperature, salinity, oxygen, nutrients, and plankton data, among many others. The data is collected from a variety of sources, such as research vessels, autonomous floats, and fixed ocean stations, covering the world's oceans from the surface to the deep sea.

The Beacon node is built on the **World Ocean Database**, available in various formats, including NetCDF, CSV, and ODV-ASCII, hosted at:

<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/world-ocean-database>

Like all deployed Beacon instances, the Beacon WOD node is made accessible via a Jupyter Notebook, which is showcased and explained in more detail below. Such demonstration Notebooks are available on the **Beacon-Blue-Cloud GitHub**:

<https://github.com/maris-development/beacon-blue-cloud/tree/main/notebook-examples>

In order to request data from the WOD Beacon endpoint, a query must be sent to the Beacon API. This can be done by making use of the newly developed Beacon Python SDK available at: <https://github.com/maris-development/beacon-py> In this case we are querying temperature,

temperature quality flag, its units, time, depth, longitude and latitude, and some metadata columns such as Institute and Platform, while filtering on time, depth and temperature quality flag. The image below shows such a query. Calling “to_pandas_dataframe” function on line 25 in the cell displayed below, automatically sends the configured query as an API request to the Beacon API which returns the requested data to the library which creates a Pandas Dataframe and returns this to the notebooks. The pandas dataframe containing the requested data can then be directly used for further analysis or visualization.

Build a query

```

1 # Here we build the query step by step. First we select the columns we want to retrieve, then we add the Filters and finally we specify the output format.
2 query_builder = client.query()
3
4 query_builder.add_select_column("wod_unique_cast")
5 query_builder.add_select_column("Temperature", alias="TEMPERATURE")
6 query_builder.add_select_column("Temperature_WODflag", alias="TEMPERATURE_QC")
7 query_builder.add_select_column("Temperature.units", alias="TEMPERATURE_UNIT")
8 query_builder.add_select_column("z", alias="DEPTH")
9 query_builder.add_select_column("z.units", alias="DEPTH_UNIT")
10 query_builder.add_select_column("time", alias="TIME")
11 query_builder.add_select_column("lon", alias="LONGITUDE")
12 query_builder.add_select_column("lat", alias="LATITUDE")
13 query_builder.add_select_column("Platform", alias="PLATFORM")
14 query_builder.add_select_column("Institute", alias="INSTITUTE")
15 query_builder.add_select_column(".featureType", alias="FEATURE_TYPE")
16
17 ## Add the Filters
18 query_builder.add_range_filter("TIME", "2022-01-01T00:00:00", "2023-01-01T00:00:00") # You can adjust the date range as needed. The format is ISO 8601.
19 query_builder.add_is_not_null_filter("TEMPERATURE") # Ensure Temperature is not null
20 query_builder.add_not_equals_filter("TEMPERATURE", -1e+10) # Remove missing values as WOD netcdf files didn't specify missing value attribute which means we have to filter them out manually
21 query_builder.add_equals_filter("TEMPERATURE_QC", 0.0) # Only good quality temperature
22 query_builder.add_range_filter("DEPTH", 0, 10) # Depth range from 0 to 10 meters
23
24
25 df = query_builder.to_pandas_dataframe()
26 df

```

9.0s Open 'df' in Data Wrangler

... /var/folders/f3/w9sk77s91rv_drj5ydspsy0dc0000gn/T/ipykernel_91685/339346104.py:2: DeprecationWarning: Call to deprecated method query. (To query, use list_tables() or list_data
query_builder = client.query()
Creating JSONQuery with from: FromTable(table='default')
Running query: {"output": {"format": "parquet"}, "select": [{"column": "wod_unique_cast", "alias": null}, {"column": "Temperature", "alias": "TEMPERATURE"}, {"column": "Temper

	# wod_unique_cast	# TEMPERATURE	# TEMPERATURE_QC	TEMPERATURE_UNIT	# DEPTH	DEPTH_UNIT
0	21960134	29.46	0	degree_C		3.0 m
1	21960134	29.39	0	degree_C		4.0 m
2	21960134	29.35	0	degree_C		5.0 m
3	21960134	29.33	0	degree_C		6.0 m
4	21960134	29.33	0	degree_C		7.0 m
5	21960134	29.33	0	degree_C		8.0 m
6	21960134	29.32	0	degree_C		9.0 m
7	21960134	29.32	0	degree_C		10.0 m
8	22012056	13.01	0	degree_C		1.0 m
9	22012057	15.41	0	degree_C		9.0 m

3,519,762 rows x 12 cols 10 per page << Page 1 of 351977 >>

Figure 28 – WOD Beacon Jupyter notebook query

In this example we can then very quickly plot this subset of the temperature data between 0-10 meters depth from the WOD collection between 2022-01-01 and 2023-01-01.

Figure 29 – Beacon Jupyter notebook query result plot

Monitoring use of Beacon instances

All Beacon instances have been integrated with the **D4Science federated AAI service**, by which access is arranged. Also, it contributes to maintaining an administration or aggregated log by a service at MARIS to gather KPIs on usage of the Beacon instances. This has been implemented by registering queries, numbers of transactions and data output, divided over original data providers, and identities of users at organisation and country level derived from the federated AAI. The KPIs can be shared through the service at MARIS with managers of BDIs for their specific data sets, so that they are informed about use of their data sets and have justification for their management.

Beacon

Executed Queries
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Executed Queries

algemeen

ID: 19428 Active: ✔ Input Date: 28/12/2024 11:40 Last Updated: 28/12/2024 11:40 Number of Updates: 0

ID: 19428

Query Time: 2024-12-28 11:34:13

Query ID: 5da73af0-b309-4541-b214-bb9f77ef1384

Beacon Instance: wb1-ts

User Organisation: National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geo

Number of Used Datasets: 7444

Execution Time (ms): 181550

Result Size: 1.01 GB

Query Failed: No

Query

```

{
  "query_parameters": [
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE",
      "alias": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE",
      "skip_fill_values": true,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_UNITS",
      "alias": "Unit",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TIME",
      "alias": "datetime",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": false
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_QC",
      "alias": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_qf",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P01",
      "alias": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P01",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P06",
      "alias": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P06",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_SALINITY",
      "alias": "COMMON_SALINITY",
      "skip_fill_values": true,
      "optional": true
    }
  ],
}
```

Figure 30 – Beacon KPI monitoring dashboard showing query performed by user

Figure 31 – Beacon KPI monitoring dashboard showing number of queries and data sets per user

These monolithic Beacon instances can be used by the WorkBench teams, but also by all other VRE users, such as Blue-Cloud Vlabs. For using, potential users have to request a token from MARIS.

Merged Beacon instances configured for WorkBench 1 and WorkBench 2

Common Metadata - Data Model for merged Beacon instances

As a next step, specifically for the two WorkBenches 1 and 2, two integrated Beacon instances have been initiated. These Beacon instances are merging data set collections from selected monolithic Beacon instances. The challenge here is to deliver harmonised collections, federated from the monolithic instances with different data models. For that purpose, the WB teams have formulated a core metadata – data profile which should be populated by extracting and mapping from the monolithic instances.

Key metadata	Description
source BDI	
unique identifier in the source BDI	SeaDataNet/EMODnet Chemistry Local CDI+EDMO CMEMS CORA/EuroArgo DC_REFERENCE+id WOD Accession number/ database ID
access date to source BDI	YYYY-MM-DD
platform	L06 (types), B76 (models) and C17 (instances)
instrument	L05 (types) and L22 (models)
variable	P01
variable standard name	P07 (if required) - could be derived from P01 or I-ADOPT mappings
units	P06
quality flag	L27 for identification of source flag scheme, and L20 (SeaDataNet) and/or L34 (IODE) for harmonisation
time	YYYY-MM-DD THH:MM:SSZ in 24 hours mode and UTC
geographic position	reference coordinate system WGS84
depth	
organisation (originator, holding centre)	EDMO code
project	EDMERP code
cruise	CSR
date update	

Table 3 – Common Metadata and Data Profile for merged Beacon instances, including target vocabularies

Remark: The header fields in this table provide information to be able to track back the data to the source BDI, where the full data and metadata reside.

Table 3 already indicated which monolithic Beacon instances will be combined into the two merged Beacon instances, one for WorkBench 1 (T&S) and one for WorkBench 2 (eutrophication).

Syntactic and semantic harmonisation

For each monolithic Beacon instance, the fields have been determined which correspond to the target fields included in the Common Metadata - Data Profile. Their content is extracted into the merged Beacon instances. This process harmonises not only syntax, but also aims at harmonising content by matching the terms (or URIs when present) used by the source BDIs to the common targeted vocabularies. The harmonisation focuses on instruments (models or types), platforms (instances or types), parameters and units, as well as other core metadata elements. For this merging, use is made of the federated queries capability of Beacon, and of the domain- and semantic expertise held at NOC-BODC assisted by the use of the Semantic Analyser software as developed and operated by NOC-BODC. Both the original content and the mapped concepts are included in the merge to help traceability and transparency.

Figure 32 – Schematic building of Merged Beacon instances by federation and harmonisation

For Beacon it is necessary to learn the required fields, mappings and unit conversions which will be formulated as filters in Beacon for efficient conversion from heterogeneous input to homogeneous output. For the formulation of the mappings, MARIS as Beacon developer and operator relies on the WorkBench teams that are more knowledgeable about the different data collections and their scientific contents. They are supported in this effort by NOC-BODC who is advising on semantic mappings and operating and managing the **Semantic Analyser (SA)**.

The **Semantic Analyser** (<https://semantics.bodc.ac.uk/>) is a software tool to analyse the semantic elements of metadata and data files from a wide range of data resources across multiple domains (atmospheric, marine, terrestrial). The SA is capable of extracting semantic content from metadata and data files encoded in various formats. Upon completion of the analysis, the SA provides a list of terms that have been successfully extracted, along with information about the matched semantic artefacts. Analyses are performed against the Semantic Analyser Knowledge Base which has been populated using vocabularies used by BDIs. This is facilitating the mapping of elements from a number of core metadata profile elements that are supported by SeaDataNet vocabularies such as platforms types (L06)) and

instances (C17), instruments types (L05) and model (L22). The development of the Semantic Analyser is shared with the EU FAIR-EASE project which serves as a development space for the Blue-Cloud2026 project. To facilitate the SA mappings, MARIS is providing so-called footprints of the original contents retrieved from the monolithic Beacon instances for the common metadata and data fields. The footprints contain the unique values as derived from each monolithic beacon, which NOC-BODC tries to resolve against the SA Knowledge Base. The returned mappings are then integrated in Beacon to produce homogeneous outputs of queries.

Figure 33 – Architecture of the Semantic Analyser (SA) of NOC-BODC

For both WorkBenches, there is a focus on those parameters that are relevant for the specific WorkBench EOVs, and striving for harmonisation of individual parameters by using their mapping to the SeaDataNet P01 BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary: <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/> and, in some cases, to the P07 Climate and Forecast Standard Names: <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07/current/>.

A new vocabulary (the EXV collection) has been created as a collection of terms used for Essential Variable concepts across the environmental domain at <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/EXV/current/>. This provides a SKOS collection for all EV concepts to be used in projects to support SKOS mappings.

Interoperability and flexible data search and aggregation functionality can be supported by decomposing the Blue-Cloud variables (parameters) using I-ADOPT. The [I-ADOPT Framework Ontology](#) is a lightweight ontology primarily designed to facilitate interoperability between existing variable description models (including ontologies, taxonomy, and structured controlled vocabularies). In 2023 the ontology was

extended to support the aggregation of variables using a range of user-defined coarser concepts to facilitate dataset discovery and aggregation into products.

Figure 34 – Enabling cross-domain semantic discovery and interoperability at the parameter level

Applying the I-ADOPT Framework means:

1. decompose the variable in atomic components
2. assign a description role for each component
3. annotate each component with concepts from terminologies

See also: <https://i-adopt.github.io/index.html>

The EXV concepts are instances of the I-ADOPT class VariableSet and can therefore be decomposed as described in Figure 3.8, and matched to components of parameters used in the datasets if these

parameters have also been expressed using the I-ADOPT decomposition approach (Table 4).

EV ID	EV Label	Property	Object of Interest	Matrix
EXV017	Sea-surface temperature	Temperature (unspecified, ITS-90 and IPTS68)	Water body	Not applicable
EXV018	Subsurface temperature	Temperature (unspecified, ITS-90 and IPTS68)	Water body	Not applicable
EXV019	Sea-surface salinity	Practical salinity and Salinity	Water body	Not applicable
EXV020	Subsurface salinity	Practical salinity and Salinity	Water body	Not applicable
EXV023	Sea level	Surface elevation	Water body	Not applicable
EXV028	Oxygen	Concentration	Oxygen	Water body
EXV029	Nutrients	Concentration	Nitrate, nitrite, nitrate+nitrite, phosphate, silicate	Water body

Table 4 – Decomposition of EXVs of relevance for WorkBenches 1 and 2 using I-Adopt.

For example, the decomposition of EXV018 - Subsurface temperature - in the EXV vocabulary gives relations with the following S21 and S06 concepts:

- S21: S21S027 water body
- S06: S0600082 Temperature
- S06: S0600160 Temperature (IPTS-68)
- S06: S0600161 Temperature (ITS-90)

Checking the S06 concepts, one can then find relations with P01 terms that have the properties “Temperature” or “Temperature (IPTS-68)” or “Temperature (ITS-90)”. In the case of the first S06 concept (S0600082) this returns 167 P01 concepts if the matrix is not specified (Fig 3.9). The results can be further filtered by including the Object-type of interest (e.g. “water body”).

The NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS)

Service Status

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Concept

Temperature

URI	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S06/current/S0600082/	
Within Vocab	BODC parameter semantic model parameter entity names	
Alternative Labels		
Definition	The degree of hotness of an object, a measurement matrix, an environment, expressed against a standard scale.	
Date	2017-09-18T16:26:	
Identifier	SDN:S06::S0600082	
Note	accepted	
Has Current Version	1	
version	1	
Same As	QUDT concepts	http://qudt.org/vocab/quantitykind/Temperature Mapping: 390580
Broader	S01:S014	parameter entity Mapping: 1450382

Narrower

P01 BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary - (167) [-]		
P01:CTMP1001	Temperature 10-minute mean of the atmosphere	Mapping: 1591289
P01:CATAVT10	Temperature 10-minute mean of the atmosphere by in-situ thermometer	Mapping: 1591271
P01:CATAVT02	Temperature 2-minute mean of the atmosphere by in-situ	Mapping: 1591281

Alternate Formats

Other formats for this page:

[RDF/XML](#) [Turtle](#) [JSON-LD](#)

Alternate Profiles

Other views of this page:

[Alternate Profiles](#) ?

[NVS html view](#) ?

Figure 35 – NVS page for S06 concept giving P01 relations

Finally, mappings and conversion rules in case of parameters and units are provided by NOC-BODC to MARIS for on-the-fly use in Beacon to produce homogeneous outputs of queries based on relationships established between P06 concepts for unit of measurements in the NVS, and matching unit concepts and unit conversion functionality maintained at <https://www.qudt.org/>.

Deployed merged Beacon instances

Two merged Beacon instances, one for each WorkBench 1 and 2, have been deployed and are made available at the MARIS server and D4Science. These are using the latest semantic mappings, and are regularly updated to ensure they keep in sync with the Monolithic Beacon Instances that provide the input data for the Merged Instances. Various Jupyter notebooks have been made available on top of the Merged

Instances utilizing the newly developed Beacon Python SDK to provide an easy to understand workflow. The following table gives the composition and URLs of the two merged Beacon instances.

Beacon instance, merging BDI data collections	Merged Beacon instance	WorkBench
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CORA Profile data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001 • CORA Timeseries, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001 • Euro-Argo data, retrieved from S3 bucket • World Ocean Database (WOD) actual depths, retrieved from ncei.noaa.gov • SeaDataNet data collection, retrieved from SeaDataNet CDI service¹⁵ 	beacon-wb1-ts.maris.nl beacon-wb1-ts.d4science.org	WorkBench 1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMODnet Chemistry North East Atlantic Collection (subset of the complete collection) retrieved from EMODnet Chemistry WebODV (Eutrophication_Atlantic_profiles_2023_unrestricted.odv) • World Ocean Database (WOD) actual depths, retrieved from ncei.noaa.gov • BGC data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_BGC_DISCRETE_MY_ 	beacon-wb2-eutrophication.maris.nl beacon-wb2-eutrophication.d4science.org	WorkBench 2

¹⁵Initially, the SeaDataNet CDI data collection concerned the SeaDataCloud T&S data product complemented with SeaDataNet CDI data sets from 2019. This has been replaced by a full T&S data collection from SeaDataNet CDI service, resulting in an updated merged Beacon instance

Beacon instance, merging BDI data collections	Merged Beacon instance	WorkBench
013_046		

Table 5 – Overview of deployed merged Beacon instances

The WorkBench teams use the two merged Beacon instances to prepare subsets and export these in a homogeneous way (concerning parameters, units, and core metadata) for loading into analytical applications at the Blue-Cloud VRE for further processing steps, such as identifying and removing duplicate data sets, validating and harmonising quality flags, and finally, generation of the highly qualified, validated, and harmonised data set collections for selected Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).

One of these analytical applications is the **webODV online service**. webODV has been developed and is maintained by AWI and is an online version of the very popular ODV software. Previously, webODV was only available as a ‘read-only’ service to browse and extract data sets from imported ODV data collections and to make plots. As part of the Blue-Cloud2026 project, AWI has developed a new version of webODV which is now a ‘read and write’ version which features many functionalities for analyses, plots, annotations, and exports.

As a standard, Beacon gives its output in NetCDF, but for webODV, the ASCII ODV data format is required. Therefore, MARIS and AWI have developed an export option with an alternative output driver which facilitates Beacon to generate ASCII ODV output files which then can be loaded into WebODV. To be able to produce an ODV, Beacon has to split its single harmonised response format into various categories such as, profiles, time series and trajectories. This splitting is required as Beacon harmonises everything to a single output format (eg. profiles, time series and trajectories are all stored/represented in the same manner) while ODV requires them to be split into separate categories. To perform this splitting, AWI has created a script that recognizes the differences between profiles, time series and trajectories. This script splits the ODV file that Beacon creates into separate ODV files. This script is available at: https://github.com/smieruch/beacon_odv_exporter. Using this script, a native Beacon ODV output driver has been developed to provide enough scalable performance when creating the ODV ASCII output. This driver uses the logic from the script provided by AWI and creates a ZIP file containing the various categorised ODV ASCII files. This has been tested by the WorkBench teams.

Beacon Management and Maintenance

Beacon is being actively developed by the MARIS team and has various releases throughout the year. Every week there is a so-called “nightly” release that has the latest features and can be used to test the stability of them. A new release of Beacon is targeted on a monthly basis, these can be minor version

updates, but also major version updates. Each release of Beacon is being built as a Docker image in the cloud using GitHub actions and once built, are published on GitHub itself (<https://github.com/maris-development/beacon/pkg/container/beacon>), accessible by everyone. Minor version updates should always be compatible with each other and can always be done without any adjustment to the current setup. Updates on major versions might contain breaking changes and might require some configuration adjustments, this will be communicated on the Beacon Documentation website. The MARIS team tries to prevent major changes as much as possible, but sometimes these are required.

Once such an update becomes available, the MARIS team will update the monolithic and merged Beacon instances on the MARIS server first. Once this has been successfully tested, the Beacon update will be pushed forwards to the D4Science environment whereby each Beacon Instance will be updated one by one.

Data updates for each Beacon Monolithic BDI instance are being done using various python scripts. These scripts simply fetch the data from each BDI as NetCDF or WebODV ASCII files. These scripts then create a Beacon Binary Format File or a Parquet File for that BDI which represent the update that either replaces the data or is added as additional data to the Beacon Instance. Beacon will automatically re-index and make this update available.

Data updates for both merged instances are being done on the MARIS server using a python notebook which acts as the harmonization tool. These notebooks contain the mappings for each monolithic instance to generate the harmonized data of that BDI as input for the merged Beacon instance. The mappings are implemented as a single Beacon Query, enabling Beacon to run these mappings in real-time and be open-source available ([https://github.com/maris-development/beacon-blue-cloud/tree/main/notebook-examples/1.5.0%20\(latest\)/harmonization](https://github.com/maris-development/beacon-blue-cloud/tree/main/notebook-examples/1.5.0%20(latest)/harmonization)) The output of these queries are stored as Parquet Files and then pushed to the relevant Beacon Merged Instance at the MARIS server.

These updates are done first on the MARIS server to test for consistency and stability. After these updates have been tested, they will be pushed towards the D4Science platform via FTP. The MARIS team will then trigger a reindex/data download of the Beacon Instances at D4Science using a "webhook". Once these webhooks have completed their action, then the update has been made successfully available on both the MARIS and D4Science Beacon Instances.

Conclusions and follow-ups

It can be concluded that very good progress has been made with configuring and deploying Beacon data lakes for multiple data collections from BDIs which are relevant as input for the WorkBenches 1 and 2. A

total of 8 monolithic Beacon instances have been deployed at a MARIS server and after testing also at the Blue-Cloud VRE.

Furthermore, two instances of merged Beacon data lakes have been deployed, one for WorkBench 1 and one for WorkBench 2. These are available at a MARIS server and Blue-Cloud VRE, where these have been tested by WB team members and finalised. Finalisation of the merged instances also required making further mappings by NOC-BODC of free text lists of terms extracted from the BDIs, assisted by the Semantic Analyser software system, and completing the implementation of the I-ADOPT approach for variable mapping. These mappings have been integrated into Beacon by MARIS for on-the-fly harmonisation of the Beacon outputs.

In addition, an export routine has been developed by MARIS and AWI to generate ASCII ODV output from the merged Beacon instances which can be loaded into one of the analytical applications, namely web Ocean Data View¹⁶ (webODV), that the WB Teams use for further processing of the Beacon output data sets.

There has been a WP3 workshop 26-28 March 2025 at IFREMER in Brest - France where the WB Teams have discussed the next steps for their analytical activities and the interaction between different tools and services in the planned analytical pipelines. MARIS, AWI and NOC-BODC participated in this Workshop and gave support for use of the merged Beacon instances.

Moreover, a management and maintenance scheme has been set-up by which dynamic updating of both the monolithic and merged beacon instances is arranged. As part of this, it is planned that the Beacon instances on the Blue-Cloud VRE will be onboarded in the Blue-Cloud Catalogue of Services, which will be exchanged with the EOSC EU node. This way, the Beacon instances can be promoted to users of the EOSC Federation.

Next to the activities directly relevant for the WB Teams, MARIS is currently working with CINECA on a Beacon instance for the full collection of open SeaDataNet CDI data sets, which should be in sync with the current SeaDataNet CDI service. The latter service includes an open data cache at CINECA, which is part of the shopping mechanism of the SeaDataNet CDI service. The CDI service works with predefined data sets, while using Beacon the functionality of the SeaDataNet CDI service can be expanded with sub-setting on the data sets which are included and maintained in the central data cache. This concerns data files for circa 3 million CDI entries which is increasing regularly as part of regular submissions by SeaDataNet data centres. An important element of the synchronised SeaDataNet Beacon instance will be that it will merge both the metadata from the CDI catalogue and the elements from the actual data sets. This will create a

¹⁶ <https://webodv.awi.de/>

powerful service which will enrich the SeaDataNet CDI service for many users and multiple uses. This Beacon instance will be deployed at the CINECA infrastructure in sync and next to the SeaDataNet CDI data cache. These activities should be concluded by the end of the Blue-Cloud2026 project (end June 2026).

In addition, MARIS together with EMBL-EBI has successfully worked on configuring and deploying a Beacon instance for the ELIXIR-ENA database with genomic data sets. Utilizing the ENA + MGnify API to gather the data and mapping those using a python script to DwC (Darwin Core) ready parquet files. These files could be directly stored inside a Beacon instance, which provided instant subsetting access to this data. Making them ready to be used directly by the workbenches.

The steps used to create this genome occurrence Beacon Instance are:

1. Query ENA API for marine samples.
2. Download study metadata from MGnify for each study accession.
3. Find applicable TSV files in study data (only for the runs found in ENA API (studies might include more), and only merged SSU OTU files).
4. Process each run and map data, first to the 'EBI internal' schema, then to the DwC schema and finally splitting into two files: relative and absolute counts.
5. Combine all these CSVs into Parquet files, one for relative and one for absolute counts.
6. Load the parquet files directly into a Beacon instance.

This provides an important step forward for the Blue-Cloud WorkBench 3 and its activities for the multi-node use case that is being developed as part of the Build-Up phase of the EOSC federation between the candidate EOSC node | Digital Twin of the Ocean and the candidate EOSC node for Health.

3. Conclusions and future plans

This second release of Deliverable D5.5 marks the consolidation and expansion of the federation model initially presented in D5.3. While the first release focused on defining the federation blueprint and integrating Google Cloud Platform and EGI Cloud Compute (INFN-Bari) as initial providers, this final release demonstrates the operational maturity and scalability of the Blue-Cloud VRE federation.

Since D5.3, the federation has been extended beyond compute infrastructure to include both semantic and high-performance data services. In particular:

- SOCIB has been integrated as a federated semantic service provider, delivering Science Knowledge Graph (SKG) capabilities and machine-actionable Data Management Plan (maDMP) interoperability aligned with OSTRails frameworks.
- Beacon high-performance subsetting technology has been deployed and operationalised, with multiple monolithic instances serving specific BDIs and two merged instances supporting WorkBench 1 and WorkBench 2.
- Semantic harmonisation workflows, including mappings to SeaDataNet vocabularies and I-ADOPT concepts, have been implemented to enable cross-infrastructure interoperability.
- KPI monitoring mechanisms have been established to track usage and provide feedback to data providers.
- Federation mechanisms have been validated in production-like conditions with autoscaling, API-based access, IAM integration and monitoring capabilities.

Compared to the first release, the Blue-Cloud federation has therefore evolved from a technically validated infrastructure blueprint into a multi-layer federated ecosystem combining:

- Federated compute infrastructures (Kubernetes and OpenStack),
- Federated workflow and analytics services (JupyterHub, Galaxy, CCP),
- Federated semantic services (SKG-IF, maDMP-IF, FAIR-IF),
- Federated high-performance data lake services (Beacon).

With the integration of SOCIB semantic services and Beacon high-performance subsetting technology, the Blue-Cloud VRE federation has transitioned from a technically validated model (D5.3) to an operational and scalable federated ecosystem. The architecture now supports federated compute, federated semantic knowledge graphs, and federated data lakes with harmonisation capabilities. This positions Blue-Cloud as a mature, EOSC-aligned federated research infrastructure ready for long-term sustainability and further cross-domain integration.

From an EOSC perspective, the federation approach adopted by Blue-Cloud demonstrates how heterogeneous infrastructures—commercial cloud providers, institutional OpenStack deployments, domain-specific semantic services, and high-performance data subsetting technologies—can be integrated under a coherent IAM, API and orchestration model. This layered federation strategy strengthens interoperability across marine data infrastructures and provides a reusable integration pattern for other thematic domains.

Future work will focus on:

- Further optimisation and automation of semantic harmonisation workflows,
- Progressive integration of FAIR assessment services as FAIR-IF tools mature,
- Strengthening operational robustness and sustainability planning,
- Expanding federation to additional BDIs and service providers where relevant,
- Consolidating monitoring, KPI reporting and long-term service governance models.

Overall, D5.5 demonstrates that the Blue-Cloud federation model is not only technically feasible but operationally viable and strategically aligned with EOSC objectives.

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